

Under the patronage of:

Organizers: Marina Boido & Serena Stanga

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SUPPORTED BY:

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3rd International Congress on

“MOTOR NEURON DISEASES: UNDERSTANDING THE PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS TO DEVELOP THERAPIES”

Torino, Italy, 8-9 November 2024

Lectures and Practical activities: Palace of the Anatomical Institutes, Corso Massimo D’Azeglio 52, Torino

PRESIDENTS OF THE CONGRESS

Marina Boido and Serena Stanga

LOCAL ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

Anna Caretto, Silvia Chasseur, Vanessa Chiappini, Javier Chicote, Sveva Dallere, Sofia Dotta, Clelia Ferrero, Giulia Iezzi, Letizia Marvaldi, Giovanna Menduti, Mariarosa Mezzanotte, Giada Musso, Ersilia Nicorvo, Paolo Pacca, Gianna Pavarino, Daniela Maria Rasà, Roberta Schellino, Elena Signorino, Noemi Scimia, Alessandra Tuninetti, Maria Veloz Castillo

ADMINISTRATIVE RESPONSIBLE

Maria Lo Grande, NICO

MEDIA RELATIONS AND WEB EDITOR

Barbara Magnani, NICO

TECHNICAL SUPPORT

Elisabetta Mancino, REAR

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DAY 1 (8th November 2024)

12.30-13.30: Registration

13.30-13.45: Opening ceremony

Welcome by the Organizers (M. Boido and S. Stanga)

Greetings by the authorities (A. Vercelli, Dean of the Department of Neuroscience, Univ. Torino; A. Calvo, Coordinator of the PhD programme in Neuroscience, Univ. Torino)

13.45-14.00: Brief introduction by the organizers

14.00-15.15 Session I – SMA disease mechanisms and therapeutic approaches

14.00-14.20: Melissa Bowerman, UK “**Considering the importance of peripheral metabolic defects in the progression of neurodegenerative diseases: a focus on SMA**”

14.20-14.40: George Mentis, USA “**Sensory dysfunction as a major pathogenic event in mouse models and patients with spinal muscular atrophy**”

14.40-15.00: Piera Smeriglio, France “**Epigenetic alterations in SMA**”

15.00-15.15: Q&A Session I

15.15-16.05 Session II – SMA: a look at the clinical research

15.15-15.35: Federica Ricci, Italy “**The backward reasoning: inputs from SMA clinical practice**”

15.35-15.55: Marika Pane, Italy “**The backward reasoning: inputs from SMA clinical evidence**”

15.55-16.05: Q&A Session II

16.05-16.45: Coffee break

16.45-17.45: Selected talks

17.45-19.15: Poster session I

20.00: Social dinner with the speakers

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DAY 2 (9th November 2024)

9.00-9.50: Session III - ALS pathogenetic mechanisms

9.00-9.20: Eran Perlson, Israel “**Unlocking ALS: Muscle Exosome Control TDP-43 Local Synthesis at the NMJ**”

9.20-9.40: Alain Prochiantz, France “**From Parkinson Disease to Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis following the ENGRAILED-1 thread**”

9.40-9.50: Q&A Session III

9.50-10.40: Session IV - ALS heterogeneity and treatments

9.50-10.10: Cristina Moglia, Italy “**ALS phenotype heterogeneity: not only motor symptoms**”

10.10-10.30: Letizia Mazzini & Fabiola De Marchi, Italy “**Innovative treatments for ALS: current state and future directions**”

10.30-10.40: Q&A Session IV

10.40-11.15: Coffee break

11.15-12.15: Selected talks

12.15-13.15: Practical activity Samuele Negro and Roberta Schellino, Italy “**How to analyze the morphology and innervation of neuromuscular junctions, by image analysis software**”

13.15-14.45: Poster session II + light lunch

14.45-15.30 Closing Lecture Clive Svendsen, USA “**Using iPSC technology and bioengineering to treat and model motor neuron diseases**”

15.30-16: Awards ceremony

Goodbye to the next edition (in 2026)!

